

Black Box or Open Science? A study on reproducibility in AI Development Papers

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Abstract

The surge in Artificial Intelligence (AI) research has spurred significant breakthroughs across various fields. However, AI is known for its Black Box character and reproducing AI outcomes is a challenge. Open Science, emphasizing transparency, reproducibility, and accessibility, is crucial in this context, ensuring research validity and facilitating practical AI adoption. We propose a framework to assess the quality of AI documentation and assess 51 papers. We conclude that despite guidelines, many AI papers fall short on reproducibility due to insufficient documentation. It is crucial to provide comprehensive details on training data, source code, and AI models, and for reviewers and editors to strictly enforce reproducibility guidelines. A dearth of detailed methods or inaccessible source code and models can raise questions about the authenticity of certain AI innovations, potentially impeding their scientific value and their adoption. Although our sample size inhibits broad generalization, this study nonetheless offers key insights on enhancing AI research reproducibility.

Keywords: AI documentation, Reproducibility, Open Science.

1. Introduction

In both science and practice, Artificial Intelligence (AI) appears to lead to significant performance increases compared to more traditional methods (Kapoor & Narayanan, 2022). Despite the well-documented claims of performance improvements, current research indicates that many papers contain significant analytical errors that alter the papers' outcomes once corrected (Kapoor & Narayanan, 2022). Researchers found that some mistakes are so substantial that the developed AIs were not usable for practical purposes (Roberts et al., 2021).

The reasons why expert readers frequently struggle to identify errors in scientific work include not only the unpredictable behavior of some AI models, but also the fact that vital information pertaining to the experiment, such as data details, and the code utilized for the experiment, are frequently omitted (Gundersen & Kjensmo, 2018). Research in the area of "Open Science" (OS) has shown that making research transparent can help reduce mistakes made by researchers (Smaldino et al., 2019), and help ensure reproducibility. To minimize errors and enhance reproducibility in science, checklists and guidelines for documenting information concerning the development of AI have been shown to be useful (Collins et al., 2015; Kapoor & Narayanan, 2022; Mitchell et al., 2019).

Lack of reproducibility is a particularly significant problem for papers focusing on developing AI. Applying poorly built or poorly understood AI models without being able to investigate potential errors can cause significant harm in practice (Estiri et al., 2022; Saisubramanian et al., 2022). However, despite studies having reviewed the documentation quality of papers that use AI to analyze and interpret data patterns (Gundersen & Kjensmo, 2018) there is still no review of the quality of documentation for papers on AI development. Such a review is important since the documentation can help to make papers more reproducible, identify errors in AI development, and ensure that AI can be adopted in practice. The research question is:

Are scientific papers focusing on the development of AI documented well enough to reproduce them?

To answer these questions, we systematically evaluate factors linked to reproducibility in research papers from three domains: information systems (IS), computer science (CS), and medicine. We find that many AI reviewed papers lack sufficient

documentation, making their research non-reproducible.

2. Background

AI and the reproducibility problem. Recently, AI has gained attention from researchers and practitioners, showing considerable positive impacts on commercial banks, audit firms, and other industries (Königstorfer & Thalmann, 2020; Krieger et al., 2021). However, many published and peer-reviewed AIs are significantly flawed, compromising their outcomes and practical value (Kapoor & Narayanan, 2022; Roberts et al., 2021). Detecting errors in science is challenging due to two main factors. First, AI derives its decision-making from training data, not developer instructions (Gebu et al., 2021), making it sensitive to biases, noise, and errors in the data. This Black Box nature of AI (Castelvecchi, 2016) obscures the reasoning behind decisions. Second, research shows that flawed results often stem from experimental errors and biases in AI models (Kapoor & Narayanan, 2022; Roberts et al., 2021), including the absence of test sets, use of invalid features, and datasets with duplicates (Arp et al., 2020; Roberts et al., 2021).

However, even glaring errors and biases are often not caught. One reason behind the inability to detect these errors is that the implementation of scientific studies is hard to reproduce since essential aspects of the implementation, including data, experimental setup, and research question, are not described and inaccessible (Gundersen & Kjensmo, 2018). As a result, errors in research persist. Thus, it remains unclear whether papers on AI development can be adequately reproduced. Given that AI models may be applied in practical settings in their current or slightly modified form, academic literature concerning their development must adhere to a more rigorous standard.

Open Science, and documentation of AI. Such rigorous standards for science in general are defined in the OS community, involving transparent, accessible knowledge shared and developed via collaborative networks (Vicente-Saez & Martinez-Fuentes, 2018). OS focuses on components like Open Access, Open Data, Open Methodology, Open Artifacts, and Open Peer Review. For reproducibility, which is replicating results independently using the same AI method based on original documentation (Gundersen & Kjensmo, 2018), Data, Open Methodology, and Open Artifacts are essential. Open Data disseminates data freely, Open Methodology involves detailed method documentation, and Open Artifacts are accessible

research artifacts with an open license (Abele-Brehm et al., 2019; Doyle et al., 2019; Jomier, 2017).

Achieving reproducibility in AI research requires thorough documentation. In software engineering, “documentation” refers to maintaining a clear and accessible record of architectural decisions (Clements et al., 2011). This record captures essential software components. For AI applications, documentation must meet specific requirements to ensure reproducibility (Gundersen & Kjensmo, 2018).

Various methods and tools exist for AI documentation, including data, model, and field-specific documentation methods (Gebu et al., 2021; Mitchell et al., 2019; Rivera et al., 2020). These tools are essential for transparency and research integrity, helping to meet Open Data, Open Methodology, and Open Artifacts standards. Table A.1 in the digital appendix lists tools for creating open, reproducible AI models. Tools and documentation are critical, as ill-constructed AI models can be harmful, particularly if errors are not scrutable (Estiri et al., 2022; Saisubramanian et al., 2022).

OS offers multiple advantages, including allowing the use of existing data and code and enabling research evaluation even without full replicability (Peng, 2011). Transparent practices also minimize errors since data, code, and methodology transparency enables faster error detection (Gundersen & Kjensmo, 2018; Smaldino et al., 2019). This yields higher quality research and effective AI applications in practice. However, due to the characteristics of AI and in particular due to the Black Box character, it is unclear whether academic studies are documented well enough to be reproduced.

3. Methodology

Our analysis aims to investigate (1) how well researchers document the AI development in their studies and (2) in which areas of OS the documentation needs to be improved. To this end, a literature review was conducted in the top journals in the fields of *IS*, *CS* and *Medicine*. To evaluate how well the papers were documented, we investigate whether the papers contain the information necessary to reproduce the results. This information is based on an extended version of the reproducibility framework presented by Heil et al. (2021). We expect that using this methodology, we will be able to tell whether the reviewed papers focused on AI development in top journals in the fields of *IS*, *CS* and *Medicine* are sufficiently well documented to be reproduced by experts. Even though we are not striving for broad

generalizability, this exploratory study gives researchers a better understanding of how to improve the reproducibility of their studies.

Data collection. Identification of relevant literature occurred in two rounds. Initially, papers were collected from Senior Scholars' List of Premier Journals and three renowned international conferences (ECIS, ICIS, HICSS) through a Google Scholar keyword search, considering papers published post-2010. Despite challenges with Google Scholar (Pieper et al., 2021), it remains a reputable engine for AI-related scientific publications (Gray et al., 2012). Keywords were defined via Rowley and Slack's (2004) building block approach. The terms included "data", "algorithm", "code", "accuracy", and "artificial intelligence", or "machine learning". The search included papers including the term "survey" in the title.

From 1,042 search results, we included only relevant papers focused on AI development with the goal of solving a problem. Within the field of medicine, for example, this could be an AI model that predicts whether a patient has a specific disease. Excluded were papers that did not develop an AI (i.e. papers about ethical/responsible AI discussions, surveys, new benchmark datasets, and new methods for preparing data) and papers that did not explicitly solve a problem (i.e. papers presenting optimized neural architectures for specific datasets). From the title, it was, in many cases, clear that the papers did not develop any AI. Titles indicating AI development were considered for inclusion in this study and evaluated in the next step, while others pointing at exclusions were rejected. Next, abstract scans were conducted. Papers highlighting AI development were included, while empirical studies (studies in which the data analysis using Machine Learning (ML) is the main contribution), non-English papers or inaccessible ones were discarded. This process, conducted Q1 2023, resulted in 17 reviewed studies.

To expand the number of studies in this review, a second round sourced from the top 18 journals and conferences in the "Artificial Intelligence" sub-ranking of the Journal Citation Report ranked by 2021 JIF was conducted. Again, keywords were defined using the building block approach of Rowley & Slack (2004). The keywords "data", "algorithm", "code", "accuracy", and "artificial intelligence" were used. In addition to that, any papers containing the terms "survey" or "framework" in the title were excluded. This search was also restricted to post-2010 publications, resulting in 4257 search results. The title and abstract scan followed the same inclusion and exclusion criteria as in the first round. After the title review and abstract scan, this round (Q1 2023),

34 additional papers were included. In total, 51 papers were analyzed in this study.

To obtain a more detailed view of the results, the papers were categorized into one of three groups: IS papers, CS papers, and Medical papers. The categorization was primarily based on the classification of the journal presented in the Journal Citation Report 2021. However, the search for papers in one journal that was classified as a Computer Science journal (Nature Machine Intelligence) resulted primarily in Medical papers. Due to this issue, the classification of the papers from this journal was based on the content of the individual papers. Table 1 presents the number of papers in each category.

Category	Number of papers
Computer Science	22
Information Systems	17
Medicine	12

Table 1: number of papers in each category.

A detailed list of journals and conferences, as well as the number of papers from each journal and conference, can be found in Table A.2 in the digital appendix. Table A.4 in the digital appendix presents the search terms for Google Scholar.

Analysis. This paper analyzes the documentation quality of AI in literature using a framework extended from Heil et al.'s (2021) reproducibility standard. Heil et al. (2021) present an evaluation framework for categorizing papers focused on AI development into reproducibility categories based on documentation details. Based on previous research, we integrated three additional questions concerning data collection, cleaning, and feature engineering; suitable application cases; and AI model performance (Königstorfer & Thalmann, 2021). These questions create a checklist to evaluate transparency and reproducibility by assessing the availability of data, models, and source code availability (Q1-3), installation commands (Q4), analysis details (Q5), determinism settings (Q6), and reproducibility in a single command (Q7). They also assess practical relevance through application cases (Q8) and information depth on data processing (Q9) and AI performance (Q10).

For Bronze classification, a paper must address questions Q1-3. For Silver, it must also include Q4-6. Gold classification requires satisfactory answers to all questions. Table A.3 in the digital appendix outlines the questions and categorization. The reproducibility framework by Heil et al. (2021) was chosen for its ease in aligning questions with different OS components. For example, Q1 relates to "Open Data," while Q4 to Q7 and Q9 address "Open Methodology".

Papers were assessed by one author against questions in Table A.3, confirming the presence of required information. If available, the question was answered “Yes”. Even with non-working source code links like in Wang et al. (2020), based on journal retention standards (Joly et al., 2012), a “Yes” was given. Referenced but limited information got a “Partial” response. This answer also included papers with non-shareable medical data (Niu et al., 2019). A “No” was given if no references or access were provided. A second author, blind to the first's findings, reviewed five papers and tried to answer the Table A.3 questions. Agreement was initially 82%, but after discussion, it increased to 96%. The team resolved the remaining discrepancies through discussion. The analysis was done by knowledgeable experts in the field of AI and ML.

4. Results

Overall reproducibility of the papers. Table 2 presents the percentage of papers from each academic field in each reproducibility category defined in Table A.3.

Label	Percentage of CS papers	Percentage of IS papers	Percentage of Medicine papers
no label	77,3 %	94,1 %	75 %
Bronze	13,7 %	5,9 %	25 %
Silver	9 %	0 %	0 %
Gold	0 %	0 %	0 %

Table 2: overview of results.

Table 2 reveals that no label was assigned to most reviewed papers. These papers often exclude references to training data, source code, and AI models. Only two papers provide sufficient information for the “Silver” label (Agostinelli et al., 2019; Xu & Carpuat, 2021), and none reach the “Gold” standard. One paper nearly achieves Gold (Agostinelli et al., 2019), but lacks information on a potential integration of the AI into an organizational setting.

Many papers without label omit basic elements like data, source code, and AI model access. Approximately a third of all papers offer neither access nor references to any of these components without giving reasons (Abbasi et al., 2019; Ben-Assuli & Padman, 2020; Chau et al., 2020; Chen et al., 2022; Choi et al., 2019; Khan et al., 2020; López-Linares et al., 2018; Munnangi & Paruchuri, 2020; Shi et al., 2020; Singh & Tucker, 2017; Teuwen et al., 2021; Tofangchi et al., 2017; Wu et al., 2021; Xue et al., 2021; Yet et al., 2013; B. Zhang et

al., 2018). Some provide two of the requested items (Ferreira et al., 2016; Niu et al., 2019; Pu et al., 2018; Twitchell & Fuller, 2019; Valvoda et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2020; H. Yang et al., 2022), while all others meet only a single “Bronze” requirement. Among “Bronze” papers, all but two lacked information about deterministic analysis and single-command dependency installation.

Across the three fields, the reviewed papers show low reproducibility, with most not reaching “Bronze”. Differences are seen in “Bronze” paper distribution: 25% of medical and 22.7% of CS papers achieve “Bronze” or higher, versus 5.88% of IS papers. Only two CS papers offer sufficient access and information for “Silver” (Agostinelli et al., 2019; Xu & Carpuat, 2021), indicating limited support for reproducibility and practical AI usage information for most papers in this review.

Reproducibility of the OS aspects. A closer examination of OS's components provides a nuanced response to the research question. Tables 3 to 5 show significant disparities in documentation across various academic fields.

Traceability of the data. Our analysis shows that 81,9% of CS, 47 % of IS, 66,7% and of Medicine papers make the data at least partially available. However, data accessibility is limited by several factors. An issue particularly prevalent in medical research is the citation of data, in combination with access restrictions due to privacy concerns (Buettner et al., 2019; Das et al., 2021; Deshpande et al., 2015; Niu et al., 2019; C. Yang et al., 2015; Yun et al., 2019). Occasionally, authors' download links are invalid (Das et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2020) or lead to empty online storage folders (Yu et al., 2021). IS papers often use publicly available data (Twitter data or legal texts) but do not provide necessary labels for analysis (Abbasi et al., 2019; Michel et al., 2022).

The inability to access certain datasets is a significant issue, even with a well-documented data collection process. Papers utilizing social media data often indicate sources and collection times but fail to share the dataset (Abbasi et al., 2019). This is problematic, since it is nearly impossible to replicate the exact dataset, even with identical search parameters. Social media users might delete their posts or account, face bans, or the platform could cease operations, resulting in data loss.

Reproducibility of the methodology. Table 3 shows the methodology information provided by the reviewed papers in each field.

Question	Percentage of CS papers	Percentage of IS papers	Percentage of Medicine papers
(Q 4)	18,1 %	5,9 %	8,3 %

(Q 5)	100 %	100 %	100 %
(Q 6)	13,6 %	0 %	8,3 %
(Q 7)	4,5 %	0 %	8,3 %
(Q 9)	100 %	100 %	100 %

Table 3: description of the methodology.

Table 3 reveals that reproducing the papers' using the information on methodology provided inside the papers is tough. Few facilitate easy dependency installation. Providing a Docker file containing source code, dependencies, and AI model is considered best practice but is rarely implemented (Agostinelli et al., 2019; Di He et al., 2022). However, most papers share key analysis details such as computational resources, operating system, AI algorithm, hyperparameters, and programming language (Buettner et al., 2019; Choi et al., 2019; Das et al., 2021; Jeon et al., 2021; Liu et al., 2020; López-Linares et al., 2018; Pu et al., 2018; Valvoda et al., 2022; Yu et al., 2021). A few document only one component or less (Tofangchi et al., 2017; Zhou et al., 2022). Many omit the operating system used for AI model training. Only four specify deterministic analysis, crucial for "Gold" or "Silver" categorization. Besides one, none allow full reproducibility with a single command (Alaa et al., 2021). Some papers, though not reproducible in one command, offer training data and source code for various stages of the development process.

Table 3 also indicates that while all papers provide at least some data collection, cleaning, and feature engineering information, the detail varies. Few cover all three aspects thoroughly (Chau et al., 2020; Chen et al., 2022; Liu et al., 2020; Munnangi & Paruchuri, 2020; Pu et al., 2018; Tofangchi et al., 2017; Twitchell & Fuller, 2019; Zhou et al., 2022), others share limited or no information (Badrinath et al., 2016; Choi et al., 2019; Ho et al., 2020; Quillec et al., 2021; Wu et al., 2021; C. Yang et al., 2015; B. Zhang et al., 2018; L. Zhang et al., 2020). However, missing data collection details are not always critical, when data originates from government agencies or is collected by certified machines and verified by professionals, assuming higher data quality as a result (Agostinelli et al., 2019; Ben-Assuli & Padman, 2020; Jeon et al., 2021; Munnangi & Paruchuri, 2020; Niu et al., 2019; Quillec et al., 2021; Shi et al., 2020; C. Yang et al., 2015).

Regarding information on the feature engineering, its absence may not be a major concern when using neural networks, as they inherently extract features from training data (Antelis et al., 2020; Ho et al., 2020; Khan et al., 2020; Michel et al., 2022; Quillec et al., 2021; Teuwen et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2020; Yu et al., 2021; Yun et al., 2019). However, the lack of data cleaning details is concerning and can impact

model performance notably (Abbasi et al., 2019; Teuwen et al., 2021; Yu et al., 2021; Yun et al., 2019). This issue is amplified in studies using AI algorithms sensitive to outliers and other errors without data cleaning information. Several of the reviewed papers that used convolutional neural networks and artificial neural networks fell short in disclosing their data cleaning process (Teuwen et al., 2021; Yu et al., 2021; Yun et al., 2019).

Accessibility of the artifacts. Table 4 displays the percentage of papers in each field that provide at least partial openness to their artifacts.

Question	Percentage of CS papers	Percentage of IS papers	Percentage of Medicine papers
(Q 2)	22,7%	5,9%	41,7 %
(Q 3)	40,9%	11,8%	41,7 %
(Q 4)	18,1 %	5,9%	8,3%
(Q 8)	9 %	70,5%	25 %
(Q 10)	100 %	94,1%	100%

Table 4: information on the artifacts.

Table 4 reveals that the majority of reviewed papers across all fields lack openness concerning their artifacts. Most papers neither grant public access nor reference the source code for training the AI or the final AI models (Q 2 & 3). Roughly one-third of all papers reviewed do not provide access or references to their data, source code, or final AI model (Abbasi et al., 2019; Ben-Assuli & Padman, 2020; Chau et al., 2020; Chen et al., 2022; Choi et al., 2019; Khan et al., 2020; López-Linares et al., 2018; Munnangi & Paruchuri, 2020; Shi et al., 2020; Singh & Tucker, 2017; Teuwen et al., 2021; Tofangchi et al., 2017; Wu et al., 2021; Xue et al., 2021; Yet et al., 2013; B. Zhang et al., 2018). However, a few papers offer access to a Docker file including the source code or model and related software dependencies (Q 2, 3 & 4) (Agostinelli et al., 2019; Di He et al., 2022). Notably, all but one paper detail the AI application's performance (Q 10), providing metrics such as accuracy, AUC, cross-validation performance, etc.

Intriguingly, some papers lacking a direct source code or model link still had repositories on GitHub citing them (Niu et al., 2019; Yu et al., 2021). In one case, a GitHub search of the paper title revealed three repositories with identical titles (Yu et al., 2021). These repositories were created following the paper's instructions, but their origin (paper's authors or a third party) often remains unclear.

Most CS and medicine papers neglect practical applications or governance details of their AI models, raising concerns, especially given AI's potential impact in medicine. However, some IS research provides examples of addressing potential

applications and misuse risks (Abbasi et al., 2019; Valvoda et al., 2022).

5. Discussion

This paper has shown that of the literature assessed, most papers provide little documentation, leading to weak reproducibility. These results are broadly in line with the earlier findings of (Gundersen & Kjensmo, 2018). Hence, despite our relatively small sample of papers assessed, we believe this evidence further demonstrates significant issues of transparency of documentation across the AI literature. Despite AI research guidelines (Geburu et al., 2021; Mitchell et al., 2019; Rivera et al., 2020), and specific instructions from journals and conferences (AAAI, 2023), many papers do not follow the guidelines closely. Researchers need to furnish more information on training data, source code, and AI models, while reviewers and editors should strictly enforce these guidelines.

Analyzing OS's components reveals different patterns. Most papers cite or provide access to training data, but some limit access to their data. Research on public benchmark datasets such as ImageNet has shown many errors, invalidating numerous studies using them (Northcutt et al., 2021b). This shows that access and references to the used data is particularly important. Since tools to identify and correct the errors mentioned in the previous paragraph are available (Northcutt et al., 2021a), it is also essential to know whether these tools were used and how the data was cleaned and prepared. However, many papers lack comprehensive methodological information. The lack of information on the data cleaning process, combined with existing research revealing the impact of errors in the data cleaning process on the results (Kapoor & Narayanan, 2022; Northcutt et al., 2021b) raises doubts about the results reported in several papers. Also, given the reliance of AI on clean and unbiased training data (Geburu et al., 2021), the lack of information on these aspects makes it hard for technical experts and reviewers to reproduce the papers. Furthermore, many papers do not present information on potential AI's, governance and security processes, and AI integration into business and medical processes. This information is essential for practical AI applications. For example, one study reportedly spent about 1.3 million euros on Cloud Computing for training AI models (L. Zhang et al., 2020). Information on (1) whether this financial investment can be recouped and (2) how users need to be protected from potential damages is essential. This is a particular challenge for the adoption of the

proposed AIs in practice, due to recent EU and US regulations that require documentation and details on AI's integration into business and associated risk management systems (European Commission, 2021; NIST, 2022).

While all three fields have similar reproducibility for methodology, they differ in data and artifact accessibility. IS literature offers limited data, source code, and AI model access but details AI integration into organizations. Conversely, CS and medicine provide minimal guidance on AI application, governance, and integration but excel in describing the data and model. The superior documentation in CS and medicine compared to IS might be due to existing guidelines and field norms. Documentation standards for AI in medicine and CS have been proposed (Bender & Friedman, 2018; Rivera et al., 2020), while IS standards lag behind, leading to inadequate AI documentation and challenges to the adoption in practice (Königstorfer & Thalmann, 2020). However, we have not deeply explored if guidelines directly improve documentation quality in the disciplines. Further research is needed.

A potential reason for non-reproducibility might be the scant guidelines from academic outlets. Many esteemed academic platforms do not mandate authors to share datasets, AI frameworks, or codes during publication. For example, in the Senior Scholars' List of Premier Journals only the Information Systems Journal (2023) requires disclosure of training data and AI models. This raises concerns about the scientific validity of publications in the other journals of the Senior Scholars' List of Premier Journals. Future studies should evaluate journal standards and their adherence in AI articles. Reviewing the validity of non-compliant publications is also essential.

The importance of reproducibility depends on the context in practice as well as in science. In practice, the EU's draft of the AI Act defines this context based on a risk approach (European Commission, 2021). For high risk use cases a sound documentation and reproducibility will soon become necessary. In science, we currently start this differentiation and we see that in high risk fields, like medicine, we have more advanced standards. However, this is a promising topic for the OS community.

In conclusion, AI documentation in the reviewed scientific publications is subpar and requires enhancement to meet OS standards. Our study initiates awareness and introduces an evaluation scheme for assessing documentation quality. Future research should develop domain-specific documentation standards, augmented by technical reproducibility studies of published papers. A compelling research direction is whether people with

different levels of expertise can replicate the paper's results with the given information. For example, Automated Machine Learning (AutoML) might assist in developing and comparing AI models and data preparation techniques (Polzer & Thalmann, 2022).

6. Conclusion

In conclusion, this paper has highlighted the inadequate level of reproducibility in the majority of the reviewed AI research papers. Even though our sample size limits broad generalization, our study provides vital insights into improving AI research reproducibility, especially considering many researchers often omit crucial details like training data, source code, and AI models. To ensure the credibility and validity of AI research, it is imperative that researchers provide more detailed information on their methodology and data, while reviewers and editors should enforce guidelines more strictly. The provision of research data from papers is critical for identifying common errors, and promoting reuse by other researchers in their studies. Overall, science needs more research on reproducibility guidelines and standards for AI research.

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